

Immediate Reattachment after Surgical Removal of Embedded Fragment: A Case Report

Farheen Malik¹, Ankur Mishra², Swati Dwivedi³, Vinod Kumar Upadhyay⁴, Ahsan Abdullah⁵, Aishwarya Srivastava⁶

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Post Graduate Student¹
Department of Pediatric &
Preventive Dentistry
Career Post-Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences and Hospital
Lucknow

Reader²
Department of Pediatric &
Preventive Dentistry
Career Post-Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences and Hospital
Lucknow

Prof & HOD³
Department of Pediatric &
Preventive Dentistry
Career Post-Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences and Hospital
Lucknow

Professor⁴
Department of Pediatric &
Preventive Dentistry
Career Post-Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences and Hospital
Lucknow

Professor⁵
Department of Pediatric &
Preventive Dentistry
Career Post-Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences and Hospital
Lucknow

Post Graduate Student⁶
Department of Pediatric &
Preventive Dentistry
Career Post-Graduate Institute of
Dental Sciences and Hospital
Lucknow

Abstract

Coronal fractures of the anterior teeth are a common form of dental trauma that mainly affects children and adolescents. One of the options for managing coronal tooth fractures when the tooth fragment is available and there is no or minimal violation of the biological width is the reattachment of the dental fragment. Reattachment of dental fragment has become possible due to the improvement of adhesive technique and restorative materials. This case describes a patient with a traumatic crown fracture of an upper incisor, associated with a laceration wound in the upper lip, showing local oedema. While palpating the tissues of the upper lip we felt the presence of a foreign body. This was confirmed by a radiograph of the lip that showed a radiopaque material, being similar to the coronal fragment of the fractured incisor. It was successfully surgically removed and immediately reattached using a composite adhesive technique.

Introduction

Around 50% of children under the age of 15 experience some form of orofacial injury or trauma. Traumatic dental injuries are a major reason for emergency dental visits, with coronal fractures of the maxillary anterior teeth being particularly prevalent due to their prominent position. On the other hand, mandibular central incisors and maxillary lateral incisors are less commonly affected. While most dental injuries tend to involve just one tooth, certain types of trauma, such as those resulting from car accidents or sports-related incidents, can affect multiple teeth.¹

After a traumatic injury, a comprehensive examination of the affected tissues is crucial. This should include a precise assessment of the hard tissues (teeth and bone) using both clinical examination and radiographs. It is also important to evaluate the soft tissues, starting with the extra-oral area and then examining the intraoral soft tissues (lips, gingiva, cheeks, tongue, and oral mucosa on the palate).² Approximately 50% of traumatic injuries to permanent incisors are associated with labial lacerations, bleeding, or other soft tissue trauma. Open, swollen, or hemorrhagic tissues should be X-rayed after cleaning to identify any foreign bodies.³

For managing coronal tooth fractures, especially when there is minimal or no violation of the biological width, reattach-

ing the dental fragment—if available—can be an effective approach. This method is conservative, esthetic, and cost-effective, and has been proven to be a suitable alternative to resin-based composites or full-coverage crowns for restoring the tooth. Reattachment of a fragment to the fractured tooth can provide good and long-lasting esthetics (because the tooth's original anatomic form, color, and surface texture are maintained), can restore function, can result in a positive psychological response, and is a reasonably simple procedure.⁵ In addition, tooth fragment reattachment allows restoration of the tooth with minimal sacrifice of the remaining tooth structure. Furthermore, this technique is less time-consuming and provides more predictable long-term wear than when direct composite is used.

The following case report describes a patient with dental trauma in which the fractured crown fragment of an upper central incisor was found in the upper lip. It was surgically removed from the soft tissue and then immediately reattached with a microfilled composite resin.

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Case Report

A 10 years old boy came to the Department of Paediatric and Preventive Dentistry Career Post-Graduate Institute of Dental Sciences and Hospital, Lucknow with chief complaints of swelling and laceration in his upper lip and fractured tooth because of trauma which occurred while scooter riding 20 hours earlier [Figure 1-4].

Figure (1) Extraoral Laceration (2) Intraoral Laceration on the upper lip (3) Fractured 21 (4) Maxillary Arch

The dental examination revealed a crown fracture on the upper right central incisor, involving enamel and dentin without pulp exposure [Figure 5]. The patient was unable to find the tooth fragment when the trauma occurred. Radiographic examination showed neither radicular nor alveolar fractures of the traumatized area. While palpating the tissues of the upper lip the presence of a foreign body was felt. This was confirmed by a radiograph of the lip that showed a radiopaque material, similar to the coronal fragment of the fractured incisor [Figure 6].

Figure 5-IOPA-R Showing Fracture of 21 Involving Enamel, Dentin.

Figure 6- A Soft Tissue Radiograph Shows a Radiopaque Mass, Which is

Suggestive of the Fractured Fragment Embedded in the Upper Lip.

After the diagnosis was made and informed consent was obtained, it was decided to immediately remove the tooth fragment. Under local anesthesia, an incision was made to remove the fragment [Figure 7]. The fragment was checked with the broken tooth in order to ensure that no part was lost [Figure 8].

Figure 7- Removal of Embedded Fragment

Figure 8-Intact Fragment

The fragment was perfectly intact and fitted well on the fractured tooth so, the fragment was stored in saline until reattached to the tooth using a composite adhesive technique. Acid etching was done for 30 seconds and a bonding agent was applied and dried for 5 seconds [Figure 9].

Figure 9-Application of Etchant to the Fragment

The adhesive was applied and light-cured for 10 seconds. The tooth fragment was attached to the upper left central incisor, which had also been treated similarly. The restoration was then light-cured for 40 seconds from both labial and palatal surfaces [Figure 10].

Figure 10- Attachment of the Fragment to the Tooth & Curing Together

Care was taken to ensure that some composite was applied over the junction of the fracture so that the fracture site was not visible once the composite was cured. Occlusion was checked, and at the end of the treatment the demarcation line between the fractured piece and the tooth was unnoticed the tooth appears normal [Figure 11].

Figure 11- Intraoral View Immediately after Fragment Reattachment.

After treatment, the patient was recommended to receive tetanus prophylaxis and to maintain proper oral hygiene, perform warm saline rinses, and follow a soft diet. Systemic antibiotics and analgesics were prescribed, along with the topical application of benzocaine and chlorhexidine gluconate on the lacerated lip.

The patient was recalled after one week, and healing of the upper lip was seen. After 3 months follow-up visit the appearance of the teeth and the patient's feedback on the procedure result was satisfactory [Figure 12].

Figure 12- After 3 Month Follow up.

Discussion

Normally, fractured or missing incisors are not difficult to diagnose but when associated with a soft tissue laceration, the condition requires a thorough examination to confirm the presence of the lost fragment/tooth which might have been embedded in the soft tissue. Tooth fragments embedded in the soft tissue may not be easily detectable, failure of which can lead to harmful sequelae.⁶ A simple soft tissue radiograph can help in the detection of the included tooth fragments in the oral regions. The treatment of choice in such cases is surgical excision. In case the fragment is intact, it can be used to restore the remaining fractured tooth. Several advantages have been cited in favor of tooth fragment reattachment. Tennery was the first to report the re-attachment of a fractured fragment using the acid-etch technique. It is a conservative restoration and aesthetics achieved by tooth fragment reattachment are far more superior to those achieved by any other type of restoration.⁷ This is because reattachment of the fragment may offer better aesthetics, as shade match and translucency will be perfect, the original tooth contours and the occlusal contacts are preserved, the incisal edge will wear at a rate similar to that of the adjacent teeth, replacement of fractured portion may be less time consuming than needed for completion of a provisional restoration.⁸

The medium of dental fragment conservation is very important to maintaining fragment hydration. Sterile saline at 37°C has been recommended as a suitable storage medium to prevent dehydration and collapse of the collagen in the fractured segment and any dimensional change.⁹ Rinsing in 0.12% chlorhexidine has been suggested as a step for disinfection. But, if the tooth fragment is allowed to dehydrate, the aesthetics achieved is less than ideal. According to a study reported by Shirani et al, teeth whose fractured parts were kept hydrated in a storage medium had higher bond strength than those whose fractured parts were kept in a dry environment.¹⁰

The techniques described in this case report is reasonably simple while restoring function and esthetics with a very conservative approach. With the materials available today, in conjunction with an appropriate technique, esthetic results can be achieved with predictable outcomes.¹¹ Thus, the reattachment of a tooth fragment is a viable technique that restores function and esthetics with a very conservative approach, and it should be considered when treating patients with coronal fractures of the anterior teeth, especially younger patients.¹²

Sengun et al. showed that reattaching fractured incisal fragments with new-generation bonding agents effectively withstands shear stresses, comparable to intact teeth. They concluded that reattachment of the fractured fragment is preferable to composite restoration.¹³

Pasini et al. reported an immediate reattachment of an incisal edge of a lateral incisor retrieved in the lower lip.¹⁴ They defined their procedure as “first choice treatment” for coronal fractures emphasizing the importance of dental fragment storage and the multidisciplinary nature of dental trauma management. Naudi and Fung reported the first pediatric case in which they described the reattachment of a

tooth fragment embedded in the lower lip, 3 hours after the initial trauma. The authors reported that there were no dental and esthetic complications for over one year.¹⁵

Conclusion

Reattaching a fractured crown fragment using bonding techniques yields excellent aesthetic results, preserving the tooth's original appearance and function. Proper hydration of the fragment is essential, and modern bonding agents make this method highly effective, especially for young patients with anterior fractures.

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